

DIAMOND - Machine- Actionable Data Management Plan

Version 0

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generation of open
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Researchers

Organizations

HOLISTIC IKE, The Cyprus Institute, ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC., THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC, ICCS, SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL, ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA'COOPERATIVA, Maastricht University, Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, KRATENA KURT, Comillas Pontifical University, The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford, Basque Centre for Climate Change, ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (ETH Zurich), Switzerland, Imperial College of Science Technology and Medicine, University College London, UCL, CICERO Center for International Climate Research, University of Basel

Datasets

Title: DIAMOND D3.1 - Initial development plan: Surveys

Template: Horizon Europe

This dataset aims to collect some initial information on how we plan to develop the new models of the DIAMOND project and link them to other tools and modules.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Models

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel for Windows

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

466.6 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To develop a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data provided by modellers of the DIAMOND project

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7774835>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

DIAMOND D3.1 - Initial development plan: Surveys

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Through the DOI in Zenodo

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinitely

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Other

Description in Zenodo

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Not available

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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